

4D comparative analysis of construction approaches towards industrialization: traditional versus total prefabrication

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to encourage higher productivity in the AEC industry by promoting a comparative analysis between very different construction approaches: traditional construction versus total prefabrication towards industrialization.

The construction of a building whose project was carried out in BIM, totally oriented towards industrialization, presents itself as an opportunity for a comprehensive 4D analysis that compares traditional and industrialized solutions (onsite and offsite construction approaches) in terms of time and needed resources.

The research concentrates on proposing a BIM-based framework to quantify the 4D analysis of this practical case study. It is focused on assessing the impacts on the planning of the execution stage, both off-site and on-site, and on exposing the detailed impacts of the industrialized solution when compared to a traditional one. The effective construction of the building in the study began in 2022. Sustainability and circularity are implied.

The suggested case study is a hotel in Guimarães that has lately received media attention due to its innovative pre-fabrication methodology. Prefabricated modules are used to construct

the building. This approach will be evaluated and compared to existing traditional alternatives. Considering this, a theoretical framework was developed by proposing a framework based on a 4D BIM comparative analysis for both approaches of construction: traditional construction and total prefabrication.

Quantifying the advantages of using prefabrication over conventional construction, By using the large extent of building information modelling (BIM) technology, and the potential benefits of using an intelligent schedule engine for the 4D comparative analysis.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/nb9iN2p9tGQ>

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